

ISic3337

Funerary inscription for Eirena

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

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Autopsy

2019-07-11

Last Change

2019-07-15 - Jonathan Prag further revised on basis of further autopsy

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Excavated in 1990; part of the cover of tomb 20, necropolis of Rocche Marina, Castel di Tusa

Coordinates

38.007468, 14.257626

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory ME 20272

Physical Description

A small slab of white marble with blue veining still set in plaster. The slab is intact on all sides, although cracked across the lower right corner.

Dimensions

Height 20.7 cm

Width 18.8 cm

Depth greater than 1 cm

Layout

Ten lines of Greek filling the available space, decreasing notably in size in the second five lines

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are engraved in a fairly plain, square fashion, with simple serifs. Alpha is mostly with broken bar, sometimes with an extended upper serif, although there is a straight bar example in line 7 and in lines 8 and 10 straight bar descending to left foot; beta is closed, with larger lower eye, generally horizontal along the base; delta varies between regular triangle and oblique lower bar with extended serif above; epsilon has straight bars of equal length, except for instances in lines 9 and 10 when it is lunate; theta is ovoid with connecting straight bar; kappa has short tails; lambda sometimes has an extended upper serif; mu varies between a form with vertical first and last hastae and short middle strokes meeting above the line and cursive form comparable to a lower-case mu in line 9; omicron is full size in the first few lines, but increasingly is smaller and mid-line; sigma is consistently lunate, but more often formed of three straight strokes; less often a single curved stroke; omega is consistently lunate, and sometimes smaller and mid-line. The eta and nu are in ligature in lines 5, 6 and 7. In line 5 the omicron in the final word is inscribed above the other letters (due to omission?). The last two/three words of the last line are enclosed between a pair of christograms. Small hedera occur in lines 1, 3, 5, and 10.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 12-18 mm

Line 2: 14-19 mm

Line 3: 12-22 mm

Line 4: 8-22 mm

Line 5: 12-18 mm

Line 6: 9-16 mm

Line 7: 7-14 mm

Line 8: 6-12 mm

Line 9: 6-10 mm

Line 10: 5-13 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: 10-15 mm

Interlineation line 2 to 3: 3-7 mm

Interlineation line 3 to 4: 5-15 mm

Interlineation line 4 to 5: 4-10 mm

Interlineation line 5 to 6: 2-7 mm

Interlineation line 6 to 7: 2-7 mm

Interlineation line 7 to 8: 1-6 mm

Interlineation line 8 to 9: 1-5 mm

Interlineation line 9 to 10: 1-5 mm

Text

1. Ἡ πᾶσι ἐν βροτοῖσιν
2. σεμνῶς τὸν βίον ἀνα
3. διξαμένη φίλανδρος
4. ὡς οὐτ' ἄλλη γυναικῶν.
5. Εἰρήνηα ἐνθαδε κέϊτε τέκνοι
6. σι στοργῆν λαμπρῶς εὐνοησα
7. μένη τριακοστῶ καὶ δευτέρῳ περι
8. πλεκομένῳ ἔτι Μοίρες βουλεύμα
9. τι, μετὰ μεγίστου κλέους τέλος
10. ἔλαχεν Βωτιβοῖο φιλτάλτη

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

ΦΙΑΤΑΤΗ on stone

Translation (en)**Translation (it)**

Colei, che fra tutti gli uomini con dignità ha dedicato la vita amando lo sposo come nessuna altra delle donne, Eirena, qui giace: ai figli affetto luminosamente ha elargito, nell'anno trentesimo e secondo completato il giro secondo il volere del Destino, con grandissima fama ha avuto in sorte la fine (croce latina) a Botis boio carissima (croce latina).

Commentary

The text offers a good example of a type of funerary inscription that is moderately well-attested in Sicily, mixing verse and prose in the construction of a funerary epigram – much of this text is quasi-verse rather than truly metrical (see Manganaro 1994 for further examples). Linguistically it shows several features which are non-standard, such as the occasional use of epsilon for eta (e.g. Μοίρες for Μοίρης) and multiple cases of iotacism. Manganaro notes that the form Eirena as opposed to Eirene often occurs in a Jewish context and may therefore signify that Eirena was of Jewish origin. At the same time, the christograms in the final line make it clear that her husband was Christian. The interpretation of Βωτιβοῖο in the final line is debated. Manganaro suggests that this is two words in the dative: the relatively rare name Βῶτις followed by the rarer ethnic Βοῖος, signifying either Pannonian, or more likely from a region of western Gaul near Bordeaux (and he notes evidence for various links between Gaul and Sicily in the Imperial period, suggesting therefore that Botis was a Gallic trader). Perrin (in AE 2006 no.514) suggests that this is instead a single word, ending in a Homeric genitive form (-οιο), and is a transliteration of the Latin name *Votivus* (and so 'beloved of *Votivus*', rather than 'most dear to Botis the Boian'). The tombs of the necropolis are dated to the late fourth and fifth century AD and the inscription easily fits within this date range (Tigano, G. 2008. *Le necropoli*. In G. Scibona and G. Tigano (eds), *Alesa Archonidea. Guida all'antiquarium* (Palermo), p.49).

Digital identifiers:

TM 645584

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-09-09): ISic3337. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4021553>

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